

Flaws in the meta-analysis on mortality in septic patients treated with vitamin C by Scholz et al. (2021)

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Comment on:

Scholz SS, Borgstedt R, Ebeling N, Menzel LC, Jansen G, Rehberg S.

Mortality in septic patients treated with vitamin C: a systematic meta-analysis.

Crit Care. 2021 Jan 6;25(1):17.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33407793>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7787590>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-020-03438-9>

There are several methodological shortcomings in the meta-analysis by Scholz et al. [1].

There are two kinds of apples and oranges problem. First, randomized trials and observational studies are pooled together as if the latter would be as reliable as the former. For firm conclusions, a meta-analysis should be restricted to controlled trials.

Second, the title states “treated with vitamin C”, but the meta-analysis pools studies that investigated vitamin C together with studies that investigated vitamin C combined with hydrocortisone/thiamine. The former studies examine the effects of vitamin C specifically, whereas the latter do not. It is even possible that in some contexts thiamine or hydrocortisone may have harmful effects and in such a case the harms would be attributed to vitamin C. For example, a recent RCT found that in heart failure patient, after the intervention, LVEF was significantly lower in the thiamine group than in the placebo group after adjusting for baseline measurements [2].

Thus, the effects of vitamin C as a single substance should be analyzed separately from the effects of the combinations of vitamin C with other substances.

Scholtz et al write in Methods [1, p.2] “*Statistical heterogeneity between the trials was evaluated using Cochran’s Q test and I-square statistic as a measure of variability.*”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

However, the I-square statistic has been shown to be flawed: "... *Those results complicate implementation and interpretation of the popular heterogeneity index I-square*" [3].

Scholtz et al write in Methods [1, p.2] "*Potential publication bias for the specific outcome was explored visually with Funnel plots.*"

However, a series of papers have pointed out that the funnel plot analysis is scientifically unsound [4-8]. A recent recommendation stated that "*funnel plot asymmetry is often, wrongly, equated with publication or other reporting biases*" [8].

Scholtz et al write in Methods [1, p.2] "*Bias within and across the studies was assessed ... using the Jadad score for randomized studies.*"

However, the Jadad score is an outdated approach to assess study quality. In the 1990s there was much enthusiasm in calculating points for RCT quality, but over time that approach lost its glamour. For example, an earlier version of the Cochrane Handbook briefly commented on quality scales as follows:

"8.3.3 Quality scales and Cochrane reviews. The use of scales for assessing quality or risk of bias is explicitly discouraged in Cochrane reviews. While the approach offers appealing simplicity, it is not supported by empirical evidence (Emerson 1990, Schulz 1995b)...

*One commonly-used scale was developed by **Jadad** and colleagues for randomized trials in pain research (Jadad 1996). **The use of this scale is explicitly discouraged.** As well as suffering from the generic problems of scales, it has a strong emphasis on reporting rather than conduct, and does not cover one of the most important potential biases in randomized trials, namely allocation concealment.*" [9]

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